

Research

The Influence of Work Environment on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch

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Abstract: This research paper aimed to investigate the impact of the work environment on employee performance, with a specific focus on the mediating role of job satisfaction. The study was conducted at the UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch, utilizing a sample of 70 respondents. Data collection involved the use of questionnaires and direct interviews, while data analysis employed SPSS, utilizing Path analysis and the Sobel test. The findings of this study demonstrate a significant influence of the work environment on both job satisfaction and employee performance. The Sobel test revealed partial mediation, indicating that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between the work environment and employee performance. Additionally, a significant indirect effect of the work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction was observed, although its magnitude was smaller than the direct impact of the work environment on employee performance. In conclusion, this study highlights the positive and significant effect of the work environment on employee performance, with job satisfaction playing a partial mediating role at the UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch.

Keywords: Work Environment, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

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Introduction

Nowadays, organizations are increasingly invested in exploring innovative and effective techniques to enhance productivity and establish a unique market identity in order to remain competitive. Among these methods and strategies, Human Resource (HR) Practices holds a paramount position, as it significantly influences an organization's overall performance and productivity. Thus, it is imperative for organizations to manage and optimize their human resources in a professional and efficient manner [1]. In this regard, employees are regarded as the primary assets of

every organization [2]. The satisfaction of employees is crucial to the success of an organization [1], and HRM strategies have been found to improve job satisfaction [3].

Employee performance can be improved through various means, including motivation, proper compensation, training, and a conducive working environment. Job satisfaction, according to [4], is the overall degree of employee expectations that determine their commitment to their work. Employees seek additional perks in addition to their positions, such as promotion, salary, flexibility, among others. These incentives and the degree of their availability may vary across different jobs, but if they are not met, employee satisfaction may decline, leading to withdrawal behavior.

According to [5] job satisfaction is the emotions associated with an individual's perception of the discrepancy between what is expected as a fair return and what is actually experienced. Another definition of job satisfaction by [6] is an individual's attitude, behavior, or opinion towards their job, while [7] view it as a multidimensional experience. The most significant factors relate to the workplace environment and the nature of employment. Employee job satisfaction is severely impacted by limited job flexibility, security, low pay, and a lack of advancement opportunities.

The working environment has a significant impact on employee performance, either positively or negatively. The working environment comprises two primary dimensions, work and context. Work pertains to all job-related activities, such as job tasks, training, work accomplishment, variation, and value of a task [8]. Neglect of the working environment has been found to have negative implications for employee performance [9]. According to [9], the work environment should ensure employee job security, healthy interaction with colleagues, acknowledgment and motivation for good performance, and involvement in decisions related to the organization's future. By providing employees with these vital factors, organizations can enhance their commitment to the organization and foster a sense of belongingness in the workplace.

This study examines the influence of work environment on employee performance at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch in Pakistan. The initial survey reveals challenges faced by employees, including a noisy atmosphere and a shortage of chairs for customers during peak hours. Furthermore, some employees expressed dissatisfaction with their salary and monthly allowances. Previous studies globally have found a positive correlation between work environment and job satisfaction, but research on the topic in the Pakistani banking industry is scarce. The studies conducted by [8], [10], and [11] found a positive correlation between work environment and job satisfaction. Similarly, [12] and [13] reported that work environment positively influences job satisfaction and employee performance. However, [14] found that a non-conducive work environment has a negative impact on employee satisfaction in the Indian banking industry. Additionally, [15] found no significant effect of work environment on employee performance.

To address this gap in knowledge, this study aims to investigate the impact of work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction. Notably, this study is the first of its kind to be conducted at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch. The findings from this study will provide significant contributions to the current literature on work environment, job satisfaction, and employee performance, particularly in the Pakistani banking industry.

Literature Review

Employee Performance

The term "performance" refers to the ability to accomplish tasks and achieve objectives. It encompasses both the quality and quantity of work completed by an employee in accordance with their assigned duties [16]. According to [17], employees' desire and flexibility in executing their tasks, can enhance their efficiency and ultimately contribute to better performance. Self-motivation is a key factor in performance, although internal factors such as essential skills, intelligence level, and resources also play a role. Therefore, organizations must provide conducive working conditions to ensure that employees meet the minimum performance criteria [18]. Several criteria were identified by [19] for measuring employee performance, including work quality, work quantity, responsibility, cooperation, and initiative

[20]. These factors collectively contribute to an employee's overall performance and effectiveness in achieving organizational goals.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a critical construct in organizational behavior, commonly defined as an employee's level of contentment with the benefits derived from his or her job, especially with regards to intrinsic motivation [21]. When an individual feels satisfied with their work, they are likely to experience a sense of comfort and high loyalty towards the organization. According to [22], job satisfaction is an employee's engagement in the workplace. Additionally, job satisfaction is a positive affective state experienced by an individual towards their current job tasks. Managers face the challenge of ensuring job satisfaction among their employees as it is considered one of the most important factors in employee supervision. Job satisfaction can be defined as a set of psychological, physical, and environmental factors that lead to an employee's affirmation that "I am content with my work." It reflects people's perceptions and feelings towards their jobs, referring to the extent to which they develop a sense of fulfillment and happiness in their job position. According to [23], several factors influence job satisfaction, and over time, five broad categories have been identified as the most crucial job features: the nature of the job itself, compensation, opportunities for promotion, management, and colleagues.

Working Environment

The work environment can significantly influence an employee's ability to perform assigned tasks. Work environment was defined by [24] as the physical surroundings in which an employee operates, their job responsibilities, and their collaborative efforts with others [25]. According to [26], the physical environment of an organization, including its architecture and appearance, can have an impact on employee workplace behavior. The work environment's characteristics, such as cleanliness, lighting, color, safety, and noise, have a significant influence on workplace dynamics, as stated by [27]. According to [28], an unpleasant and hazardous workplace, such as inadequate ventilation, excessive noise, and poor lighting, can significantly affect an employee's productivity and well-being. Workplace layout modifications can result in a 5 to 10 percent increase in productivity [29].

Based on the above literature, the conceptual model used in this study is presented in Fig 1. The model proposed a working environment as the independent variable, comprising various factors such as lighting, ventilation, noise, security, cleanliness, water availability, and relationships with co-workers. In contrast, employee performance was considered the dependent variable, consisting of the quality of work, quantity of work, responsibility, cooperation, and initiative. Job satisfaction was recognized as the intervening/mediating variable, which includes satisfaction with pay, promotion, supervision, colleagues, and work.

The hypothesis proposed in this study are as follows:

H1: Job satisfaction directly affects employee performance.

H2: Work environment has a direct effect on employee performance.

H3: Work environment directly affects job satisfaction.

H4: Work environment has indirect effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

Fig. 1: Conceptual model

Research Methodology

Research design and Sample size

The present study employed a quantitative research design to investigate the relationship between the working environment, job satisfaction, and employee performance in UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch. The population for this study comprised all 70 employees (15 female and 55 male) working at the bank. Due to the relatively small population size, the research adopted a census research approach, which involves the inclusion of all members of the population as research respondents. Data were collected using a combination of documentation, interviews, and questionnaires as the primary data collection techniques.

Data analysis method and Data Instrument

The present study employed a quantitative research approach and utilized path analysis as the statistical analysis method to estimate the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Sobel test analysis was used to test hypotheses and calculations to measure independent variables with the dependent can be mediated or not mediated simultaneously. The measurement scale employed was the Likert scale, with values ranging from 1 for negative questions to 5 for positive values. Specifically, the scale ranged from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5), with intermediate values of disagree (2), neutral (3), and agree (4).

Results and Discussion

Description of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents by age shows that the majority of respondents aged between 25-30 years old, with a total of 31 respondents, representing 44.3% of the sample. 16 respondents (22.9%) were aged between 31-35 years old, while 10 respondents (14.3%) were aged between 36-40 years old. 11 respondents (15.7%) were over 40 years old, and only 2.9% (n=2) were below 25 years old. Characteristics of respondents by gender shows that the majority of respondents in the study are male. Specifically, there are 55 male respondents, accounting for 78.6% of the sample, while there are only 15 female respondents, accounting for 21.4% of the sample. The respondent data based on working experience at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch shows that the majority of employees have working experience of 2-5 years, with a total of 35 people (50.0%). 24 people (34.3%) have working experience of 6-10 years, while 6 people (8.6%) have been working for 11-15 years. 5 people (7.1%) have working experience for more than 15 years as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of Respondents

Variable	No. of Employees	Percentage
Age	N	%
<25 years	2	2.9
25-30 years	31	44.3
31-35 years	16	22.9
36-40 years	10	14.3
>40 years	11	15.7
Total	70	100.0
Gender		
Male	55	78.6
Female	15	21.4
Total	70	100.0
Working Experience		
2-5 years	35	50.0
6-10 years	24	34.3
11-15 years	6	8.6
>15 years	5	7.1
Total	70	100.0

Description of the Research Variables

The study assessed six job performance items (Y1-Y6) on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The survey results show that the participants, on average, agreed with the statements regarding employee performance, with mean values ranging from 4.23 to 4.40 on a scale of 1 to 5. Specifically, 51.4% of the participants (n=36) agreed that they work according to established work standards, 62.9% (n=44) agreed that they work accurately and on time, 68.6% (n=48) agreed that they have successfully achieved the work targets set by the bank, 57.1% (n=40) agreed that they assume responsibility for accepting and carrying out their work, 54.3% (n=38) agreed that they are willing to assist their team members and colleagues, and 58.6% (n=41) agreed that they exhibit responsibility in their work by taking the initiative. However, the mean values of items Y2 and Y3 were found to be 4.29 and 4.23, respectively, which were slightly below the mean of mean value (4.32). The results of respondents' answers regarding employee performance can be seen in the Table 2.

Table 2. Description of Variable Employee Performance (Y)

Items	Y1		Y2		Y3		Y4		Y5		Y6	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
SD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N	3	4.3	3	4.3	3	4.3	3	4.3	3	4.3	3	4.3
A	36	51.4	44	62.9	48	68.6	40	57.1	38	54.3	41	58.6
SA	31	44.3	23	32.9	19	27.1	27	38.6	29	41.4	26	37.1
Total	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0
Average/ Mean	4.40		4.29		4.23		4.34		4.37		4.33	

Mean of the mean	4.326
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The survey results showed that the majority of participants agreed with various aspects of the work environment at the bank. On average, participants agreed that the lighting (X1) and ventilation (X2) were appropriate, with average values of 4.39 and 4.41, respectively. 52.9% of respondents agreed with these statements. Participants also agreed that the bank had a soundproofing system to reduce noise levels (X3) and a satisfactory security system (X4), with average values of 4.31 and 4.26, respectively. 62.9% and 71.4% of the participants agreed with these statements, respectively. Additionally, participants agreed that the working environment was pleasant due to its cleanliness (X5) and provision of clean drinking water (X6), with average values of 4.34 and 4.40, respectively. 57.1% and 54.3% of respondents agreed with these statements, respectively. Finally, participants agreed that the relationship among co-workers was good and motivating (X7), with an average value of 4.34, and 60.0% of respondents agreed with this statement. However, it should be noted that the mean values of items X3 (noise reduction), X4 (security), X5 (cleanliness), and X7 (co-worker relationships) were found to be below the mean of mean value of 4.35, with mean values of 4.31, 4.26, 4.34, and 4.34, respectively. The responses of the participants regarding the work environment can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Description of Variable Work Environment (X)

Items	X1		X2		X3		X4		X5		X6		X7	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
SD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N	3	4.3	2	2.9	2	2.9	1	1.4	3	4.3	2	2.9	2	2.9
A	37	52.9	37	52.9	44	62.9	50	71.4	40	57.1	38	54.3	42	60.0
SA	30	42.9	31	44.3	24	34.3	19	27.1	27	38.6	30	42.9	26	37.1
Total	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0
Mean	4.39		4.41		4.31		4.26		4.34		4.40		4.34	
Mean of the mean	4.35													

To measure job satisfaction, the study employed 5 statement items, and the responses of the participants regarding their job satisfaction are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Description of Variable Job Satisfaction (Z)

Items	Z1		Z2		Z3		Z4		Z5	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
SD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N	3	4.3	3	4.3	7	10.0	3	4.3	2	2.9
A	36	51.4	44	62.9	43	61.4	40	57.1	38	54.3
SA	31	44.3	23	32.9	20	28.6	27	38.6	30	42.9
Total	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0	70	100.0
Mean	4.40		4.29		4.19		4.34		4.40	

Mean of the mean	4.32
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Item Y1 (salary satisfaction) had an average value of 4.40 and 51.4% (n=36) of participants agreed they were satisfied with their salary. Item Y2 (promotion opportunities) had an average value of 4.29 and 62.9% (n=44) of participants agreed that the promotion opportunities offered by the bank were transparent and free from discrimination. Item Y3 (manager feedback) had an average value of 4.19 and 61.4% (n=43) of participants agreed that their manager was receptive to feedback and open to suggestions and criticisms from subordinates. Item Y4 (colleague support) had an average value of 4.34 and 57.1% (n=40) of participants agreed that they were satisfied with their colleagues who provide sufficient support to them and have good working relationship with them. Item Y5 (work interest) had an average value of 4.40 and 54.3% (n=38) of participants agreed that they found their work interesting and challenging, with ample opportunities for learning and taking on responsibilities. However, it is noteworthy that the mean values of items Z2 and Z3 were found to be 4.29 and 4.19, respectively, which are below the mean of mean value (4.32).

Validity Test

The validity test was carried out by comparing the calculated r value (for each question item, it can be seen in the corrected item-total correlations), with r_{table} by looking for degree of freedom (df) = N - k, in this case N was the number of samples, and k was the number of independent variables of the study. If $r_{test} > r_{table}$, and is positive, then the question (indicator) is said to be valid. The results of the validity test for each item are presented in the Table 5.

Based on the test results it can be seen that all the question items for the variables X, Z and Y have the value of $r_{test} > r_{table}$ (0.235) and also the probability (sig) is less than 0.05 so it can be said that all question items for variables X, Z and Y have valid and can be used in this research.

Table 5. Validity Test Results

Work Environment (X)			
	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r-table	Validity
X1	.620	0.235	Valid
X2	.666	0.235	Valid
X3	.440	0.235	Valid
X4	.466	0.235	Valid
X5	.619	0.235	Valid
X6	.352	0.235	Valid
X7	.505	0.235	Valid
Employee Performance (Y)			
	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r-table	Validity
Y1	.592	0.235	Valid
Y2	.643	0.235	Valid
Y3	.592	0.235	Valid
Y4	.692	0.235	Valid
Y5	.504	0.235	Valid
Y6	.596	0.235	Valid
Job Satisfaction (Z)			
	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r-table	Validity
Z1	.540	0.235	Valid
Z2	.556	0.235	Valid

Z3	.328	0.235	Valid
Z4	.500	0.235	Valid
Z5	.256	0.235	Valid

Reliability Test

Reliability was measured with the Cronbach Alpha (α) statistic test. A variable is said to be reliable if it gives a value of > 0.60 . The analysis result shows that these variables exhibit a high degree of reliability, as indicated by the Cronbach Alpha (α) value exceeding 0.60. This finding suggests that the measures employed in the study are reliable for assessing the variables under investigation. The results of the Reliability Test for each item are provided in the Table 6.

Table.6 Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability
Work environment (X)	0.794	Reliable
Employee performance (Y)	0.831	Reliable
Job satisfaction (Z)	0.677	Reliable

Path Analysis

In this study, path analysis was utilized to test the proposed hypothesis and determine the level of influence of the hypothesized variables on a causal relationship, based on the results of the survey.

Partial Hypothesis Testing (t-Test)

The t-test was used to determine whether the independent variable individually affects the dependent variable. The decision criteria employed for the analysis involved comparing the calculated t-test value with the t_{table} value.

- If $t_{test} < t_{table}$, or $sig > 0.05$ then H_0 accepted
- If $t_{test} > t_{table}$, or $sig < 0.05$ then H_0 rejected and H_a received.

The value of t_{table} was determined from the significant level = 0.05 with $df (nk-1)$ where n = Number of data, k = Number of independent variables. The results of the t test can be seen in the Table 7.

Table 7. Partial Hypothesis Testing (t Test)

Model		Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.946	.937	.821	-3.144	.002
	Work Environment	.796	.060	.165	13.224	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.216	.081		2.660	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance Y

Based on Table 7, the results of the partial test (t-test) can be interpreted as:

1) The influence of the work environment (X) on employee performance (Y)

Testing the influence of the work environment (X) on employee performance (Y) produces a significance value of the t-test of 0.000, less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$) or $0.000 < 0.05$, besides that the value of $t_{test} > t_{table}$ or $13.224 > 1.994$ so it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of the work environment (X) on employee performance (Y).

2) The effect of job satisfaction (Z) on employee performance (Y)

Testing the effect of job satisfaction (Z) on employee performance (Y) produces a significance value of the t_{test} of 0.010, less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$) or $0.010 < 0.05$, besides that the value of $t_{test} > t_{table}$ or $2.660 > 1.994$ so it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of job satisfaction (Z) on employee performance (Y). From the above explanation can be concluded that Work environment variables significantly influence employee performance and job satisfaction variables have a significant effect on employee performance at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch.

3) The effect of the work environment (X) on job satisfaction (Z)

Table 8. Partial Hypothesis Testing (t Test)

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized	Standardized	t	Sig.	
		Coefficients	Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.112	1.374		1.536	.129
	Work Environment	.640	.045	.865	14.238	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction Z

From t_{test} value indicate that Work Environment Variable (X) have t_{test} value 14.238 with significance equal to 0.000. Because $t_{test} > t_{table}$ ($14.238 > 1.994$) or $sig\ t < 5\%$ ($0.000 < 0.05$) then variable X (Work Environment) have a significant effect to Job Satisfaction (Z). From the above explanation can be concluded that the work environment variables significantly affect job satisfaction of employee working at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing (F Test)

Simultaneous test (F test) is used to determine how much influence the independent variable, namely work environment (X) and job satisfaction (Z) together on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). Comparing the calculated F statistical value with the F table statistic value:

- If $F_{test} < F_{table}$, then H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is no simultaneous effect.
- If $F_{test} > F_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that there is a simultaneous effect.

Table 9. Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing (F Test)

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	386.112	2	193.056	483.372	.000 ^b
	Residual	26.759	67	.399		
	Total	412.871	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance Y
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction Z, Work Environment X

Based on Table 9, it can be seen that it produces a significance value for the F test of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$) or $0.000 < 0.05$, besides that the value of $F_{test} > F_{table}$ or $483.372 > 3.13$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted so it can be concluded that job satisfaction (Z) and work environment (X) variables simultaneously influence employee performance (Y).

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) was used to determine the role or contribution of job satisfaction (Z) and work environment (X) variables in explaining the value of employee performance variables (Y). The results of the coefficient of determination (R²) can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10. Coefficient of Determination (R²) influence OF X, Z to Y

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.967	.935	.933	.632

a. Predictors: (Constant), Z, X

From the Table 10, can be concluded that the value of R Square shows the value of 0.935 or 93.5%. This means that Employee Performance (Y) is affected by 93.5% by Work Environment (X), and Job Satisfaction (Z). While the and the remaining 6.5% is influenced by factors other than X and Z which are not included in the study model.

Table 11. Coefficient of Determination (R²) influence OF X To Z

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.865 ^a	.749	.745	.943

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment X

From the Table 11, can be concluded that the value of R Square shows the value of 0.749 or 74.9%. This means that Job Satisfaction (Z) is influenced by 74.9%.by Work Environment (X). While the rest of 25.1% influenced by other variables outside the independent variables studied.

Sobel test

To find out the value of intervening, mediating or no variables, the researcher conducted a Sobel test. The value (a) and (sa) was taken from the regression coefficient between work environment variables on job satisfaction. The value (b) and (sb) was taken from the regression coefficient between job satisfaction on employee performance. To test the significance of the indirect effect, it is necessary to calculate the z value of the ab coefficient with the following formula:

$$Z - value = \frac{a \times b}{\sqrt{b^2 \times Sa^2 + a^2 \times Sb^2}}$$

- If $Z_{test} > Z_{table}$, it was concluded that there is a mediating effect.
- If $Z_{test} < Z_{table}$, it was concluded that there is no mediating effect.

Table 12 Regression Analysis (X→Z)

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.112	1.374		1.536	.129
	Work Environment X	.640	.045	.865	14.238	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction Z

Table 13. Regression Analysis (X,Z→ Y)

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.946	.937		-3.144	.002
	Work Environment X	.796	.060	.821	13.224	.000
	Job Satisfaction Z	.216	.081	.165	2.660	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance Y

$$Z - value = \frac{a \times b}{\sqrt{b^2 \times Sa^2 + a^2 \times Sb^2}}$$

$$Z - value = \frac{0.640 \times 0.216}{\sqrt{0.046 \times 0.002 + 0.4096 \times 0.006}}$$

$$Z - value = 2.6209925$$

Known value of Z-table is 1.96 with a significance of 0.05. So, it can be concluded that 2.6209925 > 1.96. This means that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of work environment on employee performance.

Results of Hypothesis Testing

In this study, path analysis was conducted to test the proposed hypothesis by examining the hypothesized variables. This approach was used to evaluate the extent of the causal relationship between the variables, based on the results of a survey. Regression analysis was done twice. The first regression analysis was to determine strength the relationship of the independent variable (independent) to the mediating (intervening) variable. The second regression analysis was to determine the strength of the relationship of the independent variables (independent) to the dependent variable by including the mediating variable (intervening). Overall, the model in this study consisted of three direct effects and one indirect effect. The results of testing of direct and indirect effects can been in Table 14 and Table 15 respectively.

Table 14. Results of Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Hyphotesis	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Path Analysis	p-value	Information
H1	Z	Y	0.216	0.010	Significant
H2	X	Y	0.796	0.000	Significant
H3	X	Z	0.640	0.000	Significant

Table 15. Results of Indirect Effect Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Intervening Variable	Dependent Variable	Path Analysis	Z-test	Information
H4	X	Z	Y	0.13824	2.62099	Significant

Table 15 shows the indirect influence of the Working Environment (X) on Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), obtained from the direct influence of Work Environment (X) on Job Satisfaction (Z) and direct influence between Job Satisfaction (Z). The calculation of the indirect effect showed a value of 0.640 x 0.216 = 0.13824.

Discussion

The initial stage of data analysis in this study involves testing the validity and reliability of respondents' answers gathered through questionnaires. Subsequently, path analysis and Sobel test were employed to determine the direct and indirect influences among the variables under investigation. The objective of this research is to analyze the effect of work environment through job satisfaction on employee performance.

The indirect influence of the Working Environment (X) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z), is obtained from the direct influence of Work Environment (X) on Job Satisfaction (Z) and direct influence between Job Satisfaction (Z), so the indirect effect showed a value of $0.640 \times 0.216 = 0.13824$. Because of the direct influence between Work Environment (X) on Job Satisfaction (Z) and the direct influence between Job Satisfaction (Z) on Performance (Y) significant, indirect influence between Work Environment (X) on Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction Z is also significant.

The Influence of the Work Environment (X) on Employee Performance (Y)

The findings of this study demonstrate a significant influence of work environment variable (X) on employee performance variable (Y), with a regression coefficient value of 0.796 and a significance level of 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This indicates that a comfortable work environment perceived by employees leads to an increase in their performance. Based on these findings, the hypothesis (H2) stating that there is significant influence between work environment variable to employee performance variable of UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch is accepted.

These results align with previous studies that have reported a positive correlation between work environment and employee performance [30], [31]. Moreover, research conducted on the banking industry in India highlights that an unfavorable work environment has a negative impact on employee satisfaction and results in a decline in employee performance [14].

The Effect of Work Environment (X) on Job Satisfaction (Z)

The study results reveal a significant influence of work environment variable (X) on job satisfaction variable (Z), with a regression coefficient value of 0.640 and a significance level of 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This suggests that a comfortable work environment perceived by employees of UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch leads to an increase in their job satisfaction levels. The hypothesis (H3) stating that there is a significant influence between work environment variable and job satisfaction variable (Z) is accepted based on these findings.

These results in line with prior research on the positive correlation between work environment and job satisfaction [8]. Managers recognize the crucial role of a conducive work environment in maximizing job satisfaction levels. Furthermore, [10] and [11] also found that work environment factors significantly influence job satisfaction.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction (Z) on Employee Performance (Y)

The study found a significant relationship between the variable of job satisfaction (Z) and employee performance variable (Y), with a regression coefficient value of 0.216 and a significance of 0.010 ($0.010 < 0.05$). This indicates that higher job satisfaction perceived by employees resulted in better employee performance at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch. The hypothesis (H1) stating that there is a significant influence between job satisfaction variable and employee performance variable is accepted based on this research.

The current findings are consistent with previous research that links job satisfaction with employee performance [15], [32], [14], [33], [34], [35]. Managers prioritize employee welfare to enhance overall performance, encouraging workers to work better and increase job satisfaction [36]. Job satisfaction is an important aspect of organizational behavior and human resource management. It can impact employee happiness, morale, and motivation to increase productivity [37]. According to [38], job satisfaction refers to an employee's preference or satisfaction with their work or work experience. Such conditions can contribute to improving the employee's performance level. On the other hand, dissatisfaction or emotional dissatisfaction with work can lead to poor employee performance. High performance is essential for an organization to achieve its goals.

The Indirect Effect of Working Environment (X) on Employee Performance (Y) Through Job Satisfaction (Z)

The research findings reveal an indirect influence between work environment variable (X) and performance variable (Y) through job satisfaction variable (Z) at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch. Moreover, the Sobel test shows that the indirect effect of X on Y through Z is significant i.e $Z_{\text{-test}} > Z_{\text{-table}}$ ($2.62099 > 1.96$), indicating that there is mediation present. However, the magnitude of the indirect effect (0.13824) is smaller than the direct effect of X on Y (0.796), which suggests that the mediation is partial rather than complete. Therefore, we can conclude that there is partial mediation in the relationship between X and Y through Z.

When employees perceive a more comfortable work environment, it can lead to improved performance. Companies strive to provide facilities that enhance employee comfort and increase productivity. Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in employee performance as it reflects one's feelings toward work. If employees are satisfied with their work, they are likely to perform better, which benefits the company. Job satisfaction is an important feedback mechanism that can impact employee performance in the future. So it can be concluded that job satisfaction can mediate between the work environment on employee performance. In other words, hypothesis four (H4) accepted. These results align with a previous study where an indirect influence between work environment and performance through employee job satisfaction was found [39].

Conclusion

The present study aimed to investigate the influence of the work environment on employee performance, with a specific focus on the mediating role of job satisfaction at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch. The research findings indicate that the bank has provided a favorable work environment and necessary facilities such as bonuses, allowances, and workplace security to its employees. The study results reveal the following conclusions:

1. The work environment has a direct impact on employee performance, indicating that a comfortable workplace leads to improved employee performance.
2. Employee job satisfaction has a direct influence on their performance, indicating that increased job satisfaction is associated with improved performance.
3. The work environment has a direct impact on employee job satisfaction, indicating that a comfortable workplace results in increased job satisfaction.
4. Job satisfaction partially mediates the effect of the work environment on employee performance, and there is a significant indirect effect of the work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction. However, the magnitude of the indirect effect is smaller than the direct impact of the work environment on employee performance, indicating partial mediation.

These findings indicate that work environment can influence the employee performance directly or indirectly through job satisfaction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed for UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch and for future researchers.

1. UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch should prioritize the maintenance of a comfortable work environment and provide employees with necessary resources, as this has been found to positively impact both job satisfaction and performance.
2. Managers and supervisors at UBL Bank Chakwal City Main Branch should focus on creating a conducive working atmosphere that fosters job satisfaction, which in turn leads to improved employee performance.
3. Future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables such as organizational culture, Compensation, training and Job stress etc that may impact the work environment, employee performance, and job satisfaction. Expanding the scope of research will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to employee performance and job satisfaction in the banking sector.

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